

FABRICATION AND EVALUATION OF CHITOSAN/PLGA BILAYERED NANOFIBROUS SHEET AS AN EFFECTIVE BARRIER FOR PREVENTING TISSUE ADHESION

Oh Hyeong Kwon¹, Donghwan Cho¹ and Won Ho Park²

¹Department of Polymer Science and Engineering, Kumoh National Institute of Technology, Gumi 39177, Korea, email: ohkwon@kumoh.ac.kr, dcho@kumoh.ac.kr

²Department of Organic Materials Engineering, Chungnam National University, Daejeon 34134, Korea, parkwh@cnu.ac.kr

Keywords: Chitosan, PLGA, Bilayer, Electrospinning, Anti-adhesion barrier

ABSTRACT

Post-operative peritoneal adhesions are common and give serious complications for surgeons. They can cause pelvic pain, infertility, and potentially lethal bowel obstruction. Chitosan is the deacetylated derivative of chitin, which is the second most abundant polysaccharide found on earth next to cellulose. It comprises copolymers of glucosamine and N-acetyl glucosamine has a combination of many unique properties such as nontoxicity, biocompatibility and biodegradability. This study was designed to evaluate the effect of chitosan/PLGA nanofibrous bilayer membrane on the prevention of post-surgical tissue adhesion. Nanofibrous bilayer membranes composed of chitosan and PLGA were fabricated by electrospinning method and characterized by several spectroscopic methods. A small portion of PVP into chitosan or PLGA solution considerably improved the spinnability of the solution. The nanofibrous chitosan/PLGA bilayer membrane with average diameter controllable from 600 nm to 900 nm was fabricated by electrospinning. Chitosan/PVP and PLGA/PVP nanofiber was gradually degraded in PBS buffer. Chitosan/PVP nanofiber lost its nanofibrous structure within 7 days of culture, while PLGA/PVP nanofibers maintained their structural feature within 28 days of incubation. After 28 days of incubation, PLGA/PVP nanofibers showed a swollen morphology resulting in significantly lowered mechanical property. Chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous membrane has several advantages for preventing post-operative adhesions. Wound contacting chitosan layer is hydrophilic, non-toxic and biodegradable. PLGA nanofibrous part acts as a support layer with mechanical strength for 4 weeks. For these reasons, results of in vivo animal study showed that Chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofiber sheet was significantly effective in preventing tissue adhesion and inducing wound healing, probably due to the appropriate hydrophilicity of chitosan layer preventing shrinkage of the sheet and appropriate barrier property of PLGA layer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tissue adhesions which caused by foreign material, inflammation, thrombosis are common complications for surgeons. They can cause pelvic pain, infertility, and potentially lethal bowel obstruction. These problems can be solved by using micro-surgical technique which minimize a scar, anti-inflammatory drug, anticoagulant, etc., but that cause delay of healing a wound. Recently, the effects of using physical barriers which isolate a wound from the surrounding tissues are reported. But the present products (SurgiWrap™, INTERCEED®, etc.) are low adhesive property with tissue, body absorption or biocompatibility.

Chitosan is the deacetylated derivative of chitin, which is the second most abundant polysaccharide found on earth next to cellulose [1]. It has many unique properties such as nontoxicity, biocompatibility and biodegradability. The living body affinity, antibacterial properties and wound recovering effect that chitosan possesses have drawn a lot of interest in recent years [2,3].

Poly(lactide-co-glycolide)(PLGA), the random copolymer of poly(lactide)(PLA) and poly(glycolide) (PGA), has been widely used for medical applications such as surgical suture, temporary scaffolds for tissue engineering, and drug carriers because of the complementary nature of PLA and PGA. Therefore, the porosity and tensile properties of electrospun PLGA nanofibers have

been characterized [4-7].

Recently, biodegradable materials have been fabricated into nanometer scale structures [8-16]. Electrospinning is one of the approaches that allow the fabrication of biodegradable materials into fibrous structures in the nanometer scale. Electrospinning provides a simple and versatile method to generate ultrathin fiber from various materials that include polymers, composites and ceramics. The detailed mechanism of electrospinning, including jet initiation, growth of bending instability, elongation of the jet and solidification of the jet into the nanofiber has been investigated comprehensively.

In the present work, biodegradable chitosan/PLGA nanofibrous bilayer membrane containing nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug was fabricated by electrospun method for application to the prevention of post-surgical tissue adhesion.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The paper should be written following the format of this template. The file has to be translated into Portable Document Format (PDF) before submission. Chitosan(95%, deacetylated, 9 cPs) was purchased from Chitopia(Samsung Chitopia, Korea). Poly(lactide- co-glycolide) (PLGA) was purchased from Boehringer Ingelheim, Ingelheim, (Resomer® RG 509s, inherent viscosity 1.6dl/g, Germany). Poly(vinyl pyrrolidone)(PVP, Mw = 360,000) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Korea).

2.2 Electrospinning process

Chitosan and PVP were dissolved in concentrated aqueous acetic acid(90%) at various concentrations. PLGA and PVP were dissolved in acetone and DMF to fabricate nanofibers,. The electrospinning was performed at 25 °C and polymer solution was placed into a 10 ml syringe with a 21 gauge needle. A high-voltage DC generator was used to generate voltage up to 30 kV. An electric field was created with high voltage power supply at 15~20 kV. Distance between the needle and the collector was 10~12 cm and flow rate of the solution was 2 ml/h. The electrospun chitosan/PVP nanofibers were washed with acetone to remove acetic acid and dried under vacuum at room temperature overnight. After drying chitosan/PVP, it is layered with electrospun PLGA/PVP. And this bilayered nanofiber sheet was dried under vacuum at room temperature overnight

2.3 Characterization of electrospun nanofibers

Morphological structures of electrospun nanofibers were observed using scanning electron microscope(SEM JSM-6380, d=3.0 nmb, JEOL, Japan) after sputter-coating with platinum. The average diameter of electrospun nanofibers was determined by image analyzer (TDISE Version 3.7.73). Attenuated total reflection-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR: Vertex 80v, Hyperion 2000, Bruker Biospin, Germany) and electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis (ESCA; Quantera SXM, ULVAC-PHI, Japan) were used to characterize chemical structure of electrospun nanofibers.

2.4 Biodegradation studies

The paper should be written following the format of this template. The file has to be translated into Portable Document Format (PDF) before submission. Electrospun nanofibers of chitosan/PVP and PLGA/PVP were cut into a circle shape with 20 mm in diameter as specimen for shrinkage test. Specimens were placed on table and then spray specimens with PBS by sprayer sufficiently. Three samples in each group dried at room temperature for 10 minutes. The sizes of the dried specimens were measured and compared with the initial size.

For the degradation test, the electrospun specimens(1 x 1 cm) were put in closed conical tube containing 10 ml of phosphate buffer solution (PBS, pH 7.4, 37°C) for different periods of time. The

samples were then dried in a vacuum oven at 25°C for 12 hours to monitor structural deformation and morphology of nanofibers.

2.5 Animal study

A total of 45 outbred Sprague-Dawley rats (230-280 g) were used for this study. To evaluate the effects of nanofibrous sheet as physical barrier for the prevention of intra-abdominal adhesion in a rat model, we divided 45 male rats into three equal groups. In group 1 (control) the defect was not treated; in group 2 the defect was treated with chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous sheet; in group 3 the defect was treated with chitosan/PVP monolayer. Adhesion model was made on both sides of the abdominal wall and cecum. Animals were given free access to the food and water. The presence of adhesion between the cecum and the peritoneal wall was assessed 4 weeks after surgery. Adhesions were scored using Nair's method [16]: 0=No adhesions, 1=Single band of adhesion, 2=Two bands of adhesion, 3=More than 2 bands or whole of intestines forming a mass, 4=Viscera directly adherent to abdominal wall.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

The average diameter of chitosan/PVP and PLGA/PVP nanofibers was 498 and 691 nm, respectively. Chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous sheets were fabricated by electrospinning of each polymer solution. (Fig. 1) All nanofiber sheets are observed to have porous 3D nonwoven mat structures.

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of electrospun nanofibers of a) chitosan/PVP, b) PLGA/PVP.

3.2 Biodegradation test

PLGA nanofiber significantly shrank after immersion in PBS buffer, while no size reduction is observed in PLGA/PVP and chitosan/PVP nanofibers probably due to the hydrophilic nature of added PVP. Hydrophobic PLGA nanofiber showed shrinkage behavior in PBS. As results, application of PLGA could be limited in tissue engineering area due to dramatic size reduction. In contrast,

application of chitosan/PVP and PLGA/PVP nanofibrous sheets could be utilized on tissue engineering field.

Fig. 2. SEM photomicrographs of degraded a) chitosan/PVP and b) PLGA/PVP nanofibrous sheets as a function of incubation time at 37°C in PBS.

Chitosan/PVP and PLGA/PVP nanofiber was gradually degraded in PBS buffer. Fig. 2 shows the SEM photographs of each electrospun nanofiber after biodegradation experiment as a function of incubation time. Chitosan/PVP nanofiber lost its nanofibrous structure within 7 days of culture, while PLGA/PVP nanofibers maintained their structural feature within 28 days of incubation. After 28 days of incubation, PLGA/PVP nanofibers showed a swollen morphology resulting in significantly lowered mechanical property. Generally, an operation wound recovered with 7-10 days after surgery, so biodegradation behavior of chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous sheet is adequate to act as an physical barrier to prevent post-operative tissue adhesion.

3.3 Animal study

The formation of tissue adhesion between cecum and the abdominal wall was examined by Nair's method.[16](Table 1) Chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous membrane has several advantages for preventing post-operative adhesions. Wound contacting chitosan layer is hydrophilic, non-toxic and biodegradable. PLGA nanofibrous part acts as a support layer with mechanical strength for 4 weeks. For these reason, results of in vivo animal study showed that chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofiber sheet was significantly effective in preventing tissue adhesion and inducing wound healing, probably due to the appropriate hydrophilicity of chitosan layer preventing shrinkage of the sheet and appropriate barrier property of PLGA layer.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the electrospinning technique was used to fabricate chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous sheet for biomedical applications. The effects of solution and processing parameters on the morphology of electrospun nanofibers were investigated. Addition of PVP into chitosan or PLGA solution considerably improved the spinnability of the solution. From the in vivo animal study, tissue adhesion between cecum and abdominal wall is dramatically decreased by applying a chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous sheet on surgery. Chitosan/PLGA bilayered nanofibrous mats hold a great potential to prevent post-surgical adhesions.

Table 1. Comparison of abdominal adhesion on animal study (n=10)

Experiment Set	Score	Control	Chitosan/PVP-PLGA/PVP Bilayer	Chitosan Monolayer
	0	0	10	8
	1	0	0	0
	2	0	0	0
	3	2	1	2
	4	8	0	1
	Mean of score	3.8	0.3	0.9
	Anti-adhesion (%)	0%	91%	73%

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